

COLOR AS A LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CODE: FEATURES OF ITS PERCEPTION IN UZBEK AND SPANISH PROVERBIAL WISDOM

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 21 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 10 Oct 2024

Abstract: This article explores the concept of color as a cultural code within Uzbek and Spanish proverbs. In every culture, colors hold symbolic meanings that reflect national values, traditions, and worldviews. The article provides a comparative analysis of the semantics of color in both linguistic cultures, highlighting similarities and differences in the symbolic meaning of colors and the peculiarities of their perception in Uzbek and Spanish proverbs. It examines how color serves as an important element of cultural identity and its expression through proverbs.

Keywords: color, cultural code, proverbs, Uzbek culture, Spanish culture, linguistic culture, color semantics.

Color as a phenomenon of human culture is not only a physical phenomenon, but also an important symbolic tool in the transmission of cultural and national values. In different societies, the meaning of color varies depending on historical, geographical, religious and social factors, forming unique perceptions in each culture. This article examines how color is used in folk wisdom through the proverbs of two different cultures — Uzbek and Spanish.

Proverbs, being an integral part of folklore, reflect the centuries-old experience of peoples, conveying norms, values and worldview. The semantics of color in proverbs often indicate the symbolism inherent in a particular cultural context, which can vary significantly depending on the national picture of the world. Color has a symbolic function, expressing cultural meanings inherent in a certain group of people. In proverbs, color is often used to denote specific emotional states, social phenomena, or moral lessons. For example, red can symbolize danger, passion or love, and black can be associated with sadness or evil. In each culture, these meanings can change, acquiring a specific national connotation.

Uzbek culture is rich in the symbolism of color, which is especially evident in folklore. The colors not only reflect the environment, but are also closely related to the spiritual and religious life of the people. In Uzbek proverbs, red is often associated with strength, courage and sometimes with negative connotations, whereas white is associated with purity and virtue. In Spanish culture, colors also play an important role in folk expressions. For example, the color red is often associated with vitality and passion, which is closely related to the Spanish fiesta and bullfighting traditions.

Black often symbolizes mourning and sorrow, which reflects the strong influence of the Catholic tradition. In Uzbek proverbs, colors play an important role in conveying wisdom and life experience. For example, proverbs such as "Kora kyz ermas" (Black eyes do not deceive) or "Ok yil" (White Road) demonstrate positive and negative connotations of colors. It is

important to note that in Uzbek culture, color often carries a metaphorical meaning associated with traditions and history.

Spanish proverbs are rich in color symbols, and colors in them are often used to emphasize an emotional state or a moral lesson. For example, the proverb "Verde y con asas, alcarraza" (Green and with handles, jug) is a symbol of caution and distrust, and black in proverbs often symbolizes sadness or grief. In the studied Uzbek and Spanish cultures, both common features and differences in the perception of colors can be distinguished. Some colors, such as white, red and black, have acquired similar meanings in both cultures due to their universal symbolic meaning associated with natural and religious phenomena.

The white color, for example, symbolizes purity, kindness and spirituality in both cultures. The Uzbek proverb "Ok yil!" (White Road) expresses the wish of good luck and success. This echoes the Spanish proverb "Salió con la frente blanca" (He came out with a white forehead), where the white color represents honor and honesty. The color red also often symbolizes energy, strength and passion. In the Spanish proverb "Tener sangre en las venas" (To have blood in your veins), red is associated with vitality and activity. In Uzbek culture, red can mean both positive qualities — courage and determination, and negative ones — danger, aggression, which is illustrated by the proverb "Kizil kyzdan kyrk" (Be afraid of the red eye). Black, on the other hand, is perceived differently in these two cultures.

In Spanish culture, black symbolizes mourning, sadness and death, which is confirmed by the proverb "Ir de negro" (To go in black), meaning sorrow or mourning. In Uzbek proverbs, black sometimes has more neutral or even positive connotations. For example, the proverb "Kora kyz ermas" (Black eyes do not deceive) connects black with honesty and sincerity, which represents the opposite symbolism compared to Spanish culture.

The environment has a significant impact on the perception of color in culture. In Spain, where the sun and the bright colors of nature play an important role, colors are often associated with life cycles, holidays and folk traditions. This is especially noticeable on holidays such as the Fiesta de San Fermin, where red and white symbolize passion and spiritual purity. These colors reflect a culture based on emotional intensity and expression.

In Uzbekistan, nature also plays an important role in the formation of color symbols. Green, for example, is traditionally associated with fertility, spring and prosperity, which is associated with the agricultural traditions of the country. The Uzbek proverb "Kyk kyz kerak bilsa, kynglinga kara" (If you want to see green eyes, look into the heart) reflects the close connection of color with nature and mental state.

Comparing Uzbek and Spanish proverbs, it is possible to note both the common symbolic meanings of color and cultural differences. In both cultures, white symbolizes purity, but the perception of red or black varies. Uzbek culture gives black more positive connotations in the context of honesty and frankness, whereas in Spanish culture this color is often associated with mourning and negativity. For Spanish culture, the most important role is played by the emotional saturation of the symbolism of color, which is associated with climate, history and religion.

The influence of Catholicism on the perception of black and white colors can be seen in proverbs and sayings, where black symbolizes death and mourning, and white symbolizes spiritual purity. Yellow and orange colors, despite their proximity in spectrum, play a different role in Uzbek and Spanish proverbial wisdom.

In Uzbek culture, yellow can be associated with autumn, maturity and completion of the life stage, which is associated with the agrarian tradition and the seasonal cycle. For example, the proverb "Sarik shtmai, eat shtmaydi" (Yellow will not disappear, as youth will not pass) indicates the inevitability of aging and changing life cycles. Yellow here metaphorically

expresses the transition from youth to maturity. In Spanish proverbs, yellow is more often associated with envy, betrayal and a warning of danger. For example, the expression "Amarillo de envidia" (Yellow with envy) clearly indicates the negative emotional connotation of this color. This is due to the cultural heritage of the Mediterranean, where yellow is associated with illness or infidelity, possibly due to associations with the color of yellowed faces of patients.

Orange is not a common color in Uzbek proverbs, but in Spanish proverbs it often symbolizes energy, warmth and the sun, which is associated with the sunny climate of Spain. Expressions associated with the orange color can also emphasize wealth and fertility, for example, the proverb "Naranja de oro, buena como el oro" (An orange is golden, as gold is good), indicates the value and significance of the harvest. The perception of blue and green in Uzbek and Spanish proverbs shows a strong connection with nature and spiritual values. The green color in Uzbek culture is deeply rooted in religious and symbolic traditions. It is often associated with life, prosperity, healing and holiness.

In Islam, the green color symbolizes paradise and divine blessing, which is reflected in proverbs such as "Zilol suvda, yashil shtda baraka" (In clean water — life, in green grass — grace). Here, green represents a sign of abundance and natural order. In Spanish culture, green is also associated with nature, but in some contexts it may have negative connotations. For example, the expression "Estar verde" (to be green) means immaturity or inexperience, which contrasts with the positive symbolism of this color in Uzbek culture.

At the same time, blue in both cultures is often associated with infinity, sky and tranquility. The Uzbek proverb "Kyk — tangring yuzidir" (Blue is the face of God) emphasizes the greatness and incomprehensibility of heaven as a divine manifestation. In Spanish culture, blue also symbolizes stability and tranquility, but can also be associated with melancholy. For example, the expression "Estar azul" (to be blue) describes a person in a state of sadness or depression, which is similar to the English "feeling blue". Comparative analysis shows that blue in both cultures symbolizes both positive and negative emotional states.

The religious factor also has a significant impact on the perception of colors in both cultures. In Spanish culture, the influence of the Catholic Church has conditioned the symbolism of white and black as colors denoting purity and mourning, respectively. In Uzbek culture, under the influence of Islam, the green color has acquired a sacred meaning, symbolizing paradise and divine blessing. White is also associated with purity and holiness, but on a broader social and spiritual plane. Uzbek culture largely reflects steppe, agricultural traditions, where symbols of fertility and natural cycles play an important role.

This can be seen in the use of green, which symbolizes life and prosperity, as well as in the meaning of white as a symbol of good luck and blessing. The perception and use of color in Uzbek and Spanish proverbs shows that color symbols play a key role in the formation of national cultural codes. The analysis of color in proverbial wisdom allows a deeper understanding of the worldview and cultural values of peoples. Uzbek and Spanish proverbs, despite cultural differences, show common features in the symbolism of color, reflecting human emotions and experience.

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